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Synthesis of Hydrazones of *o*-Ethylmalonanilic Acid Hydrazide as Antitubercular Compounds

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ISONICOTINIC acid hydrazide¹ and its N'-isopropyl derivative are effective drugs in the treatment of human tuberculosis. Although tuberculostatic activity has been shown by some other pyridine and non-pyridine hydrazides none is found superior to isonicotinic acid hydrazide. With a view to reduce toxicity due to free amino group, the condensation products of a number of hydrazides with various aldehydes and ketones were also examined². Hydrazones have been found to possess antibacterial activity^{3,4}. In addition they have also been reported to possess antifungal^{5,6,7} as well as insecticidal activity^{8,9,10,11}. A number of hydrazones have been synthesised through the condensation of *o*-ethylmalonanilic acid hydrazide with a number of aldehydes and ketones. The hydrazide was obtained by the action of hydrazine hydrate on *o*-ethylmalonanilate. The latter was obtained by condensing *o*-ethylaniline^{1,2} with ethyl malonate. Hydrazones were obtained in the usual way.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected.

o-Ethylmalonanilate : *o*-Ethylaniline (3.6 g) and ethyl malonate (7.2 g) were taken in a round bottomed flask and the mixture heated to very gentle ebullition with an air condenser. After one hour the mixture was cooled and 10 ml of ethanol was added. The crystals of the dianilide which separated were recrystallised from petroleum ether, m.p. 68°, yield 2.83 g (40%). (Found : C, 65.78 ; H, 7.02 ; N, 5.52 C₁₃H₁₇NO₂ requires : C, 66.38 ; H, 7.23 ; N, 5.95%).

o-Ethylmalonanilic acid hydrazide : To *o*-ethylmalonanilate (2 g) dissolved in absolute alcohol (10 ml), 99% hydrazine hydrate (2 ml) was added dropwise with constant stirring. This mixture was set aside for one hour and the solid separated was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 156°, yield 97%.

(Found : C, 60.30 ; H, 6.24 ; N, 18.77 C₁₁H₁₅N₃O₂ requires : C, 59.72 ; H, 6.78 ; N, 19.00%).

Preparation of Hydrazones : An alcoholic solution of equimolecular quantities of aldehyde or ketone and *o*-ethylmalonanilic acid hydrazide were refluxed on a water bath for 2 hrs. The reaction mixture was cooled and the solid was filtered, washed with alcohol and crystallised from alcohol-acetic acid (Table 1).

TABLE 1

R	X	Yield (%)	m.p. (°C)	Formula	Analysis (%) Found Calcd.
Phenyl	H	99	235	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₂	C 69.72 69.90 H 5.86 6.14 N 13.24 13.59
2-nitrophenyl	H	51	222	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₄	C 60.58 61.01 H 4.80 5.09 N 15.26 15.65
3-nitrophenyl	H	49	220	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₄	C 60.52 61.01 H 5.13 5.09 N 15.42 15.65
4-nitrophenyl	H	60	265	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₄	C 60.72 61.01 H 4.93 5.09 N 15.62 15.65
2-hydroxyphenyl	H	99	220	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₃	C 66.18 66.46 H 5.72 5.84
4-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl	H	67	195	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₄	C 63.89 64.22 H 5.22 5.91 N 11.29 11.83
Phenylvinyl	H	98	206	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₂	C 71.06 71.64 H 5.73 6.26 N 11.96 12.53
Furfuryl	H	93	227	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₃	C 63.89 64.21 H 5.30 5.69 N 13.67 14.05
Thiophenyl	H	70	207	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	C 60.72 60.90 H 5.10 5.09 N 12.89 13.01
Trichloromethyl	H	47	152	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ O ₂ Cl ₃	C 44.86 44.50 H 3.60 3.99 O 70.62 71.21
4-methylphenyl	CH ₃	88	188	C ₂₀ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₂	H 6.33 6.82

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and thiazole-2-malonamic acid with salicylaldehyde and substituted salicylaldehydes using trace of pyridine or piperidine as condensing agent. Some of the coumarins and Schiff's bases synthesised have been tested for their antibacterial and antifungal activity. Some earlier workers have reported the chemotherapeutic value⁴⁻⁷ of coumarins and Schiff's bases.

Some New Coumarins and Schiff's Bases as Possible Antibacterial and Antifungal Agents

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Experimental

Condensation of Malon-3-chloro-2-methoxy anilic acid with Salicylaldehyde : Formation of Coumarin-3-carboxy (3-chloro-2-methoxy) anilide and 2-hydroxy benzal (3-chloro-2-methoxy) aniline :

Malon-3-chloro-2-methoxy anilic acid (1.2 g), salicylaldehyde (0.6 g) and a drop of pyridine were heated in an oil bath at 80° for four hrs. The yellow solid mass was then digested with a saturated solution of sodium bicarbonate (10 ml). The alkali extract was decanted and the residue washed well with water. The alkali extract on acidification with HCl (conc.) did not form any precipitate. The residue was then boiled with ethanol (15 ml) and

IN our earlier communications we described the preparation of some new malon anilic acids^{1, 2}, coumarins and Schiff's bases³. The present paper deals with the synthesis of some new coumarins and Schiff's bases by condensing malon *o*-pheneticid, 3-chloro-2-methyl, 3-chloro-2-methoxy anilic acids

TABLE I

Sl. No.	R	R ₁	R ₂	m.p. (°C)	Nitrogen%		m.p. (°C)	Nitrogen%	
					Found	Calcd.		Found	Calcd.
1.	<i>o</i> -OC ₂ H ₅ .C ₆ H ₄ -	H	H	200	4.39	4.53	—	—	—
2.	"	Cl	H	218	3.92	4.07	93	4.94	5.08
3.	"	Cl	Cl	233	3.78	3.70	84	4.45	4.51
4.	"	Br	H	207	3.80	3.60	87	4.30	4.37
5.	"	Br	Br	220	2.79	2.99	108	3.26	3.50
6.	"	I	I	267	2.11	2.49	150	2.93	2.84
7.	"	H	NO ₂	232	8.47	7.91	128	9.14	9.79
8.	"	NO ₂	NO ₂	278	10.25	10.52	250	12.23	12.69
9.	3-Cl-2-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₃ -	H	H	232	4.40	4.46	103	5.35	5.70
10.	3-Cl-2-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₃ -	Cl	H	252	3.45	4.02	102	5.63	5.00
11.	"	Cl	Cl	288	3.48	3.65	146	4.92	4.45
12.	"	Br	H	237	3.38	3.56	105	4.33	4.31
13.	"	Br	Br	224	3.27	2.96	151	3.37	3.46
14.	"	I	I	202	2.62	2.47	196	2.59	2.81
15.	"	NO ₂	H	268	7.17	7.81	185	9.52	9.64
16.	3-Cl-2-OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₃ -	Cl	H	253	3.50	3.85	118	4.69	4.74
17.	"	Cl	Cl	262	3.68	3.52	121	4.05	4.24
18.	"	Br	H	238	2.95	3.42	105	3.63	4.11
19.	"	Br	Br	214	2.26	2.87	109	3.20	3.33
20.	"	I	I	251	1.95	2.40	69	2.46	2.72
21.	"	NO ₂	H	277	7.31	7.47	176	8.61	9.13
22.	"	Cl	NO ₂	261	7.15	6.86	212	8.83	8.23
23.	C ₆ H ₄ NS(2')	Cl	H	205	9.04	9.14	128	11.68	11.74
24.	"	Cl	Cl	214	7.58	8.23	108	10.10	10.29
25.	C ₆ H ₄ NS(2')	Br	H	202	7.37	7.97	114	9.27	9.89
26.	"	Br	Br	194	6.73	6.51	148	7.51	7.77
27.	"	I	I	—	—	—	187	6.53	6.14
28.	"	NO ₂	H	226	12.92	13.24	198	17.20	16.86

1. All the melting points are taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected.
 2. All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and halogen/sulphur analyses.